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**OPPRESSION OF WOMEN IN NORTHERN NIGERIAN FICTION: A STUDY OF
ZAYNAB ALKALI'S *THE DESCENDANTS* AND ABUBAKAR GIMBA'S *SACRED
APPLES***

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ABSTRACT

This paper focused on the oppression of women in Northern Nigeria using creative works of two foremost Northern Nigerian writers. Research showed that many Nigeria writers have written several works, particularly on the oppression of women. However, Northern Nigeria has not been adequately explored by critics of Nigerian literary works. It is based on the above gap that the study examined oppression of women in Northern Nigeria in Zaynab Alkali's *The Descendants* and Abubakar Gimba's *Sacred Apples* with the aim of exploring the condition of women and girls in the Northern region. The theoretical framework adopted for this study is feminism because of its ability to engender gender balancing in society. The study showed that oppression of women and girls in the region is sustained through the instruments of religion and culture. It also revealed that oppression of women is not inherently due to Islamic teaching, rather it is rooted and perpetuated by men who interpret and use Islamic teachings to justify their power and control over women. The study recommends that early marriage be discouraged. Girls should be allowed to go to school, after which they can choose who to marry. More women should be empowered to contribute more to the development of their societies.

Keywords: Oppression of Women, Northern Nigerian Fiction, Zaynab Alkali, Abubakar Gimba

INTRODUCTION

The focus of this paper is on the oppression of women in Northern Nigeria. In terms of coverage of literary works, Northern Nigeria has not been adequately explored by critics of Nigerian literary works as attested to by Abdu who pointed to the relative academic neglect of works from the region (1), and Omoha who said that "Northern Nigeria is certainly disadvantaged in growth of the literary typology compared to East, South, and West of the country when the relationship between written and oral literature comes to focus" (2). In fact, most of the compendiums on Nigerian literature "reveal a loud absence of a significant Northern Nigerian presence" (Omoha, 3). In addition, there is absence of documented information on writers from the region (Omoha, 4). Many Northern Nigerian scholars and critics have written, and many are still writing but they are yet to receive the needed critical attention. Thus, in contrast to the Southern part of the country, the North has produced so many literary writers that have not made it to the vast and voluminous critical works of Nigerian literature (Abel, 4).

However, in terms of oppression of Northern Nigerian women, both male and female writers from the region have deployed the medium of literature, particularly the fictional novel to depict the different socio-cultural and religious challenges faced by women because of their sex. These works however do not delve into the ways in which the woman can be liberated, but merely state the current calamitous scenario she finds herself in. This study attempts to bridge the gap by identifying how the authors of the selected texts empower and liberate the protagonists in their fictive endeavours. The study critically examines how Zaynab Alkali and Abubakar Gimba view Western education and its relationship to individual and societal development. It assesses the plight of women in cultural, economic and religious society, to see how they individually deal

with early marriage, teenage pregnancy, arranged marriages, polygamy, divorce and other manifestations of female oppression.

Abel Joseph observes that most, if not all recommended Nigerian novels are written by authors from the western and southern parts of Nigeria (3). Thus, many Nigerian creative works and criticism have focused majorly on writers from South eastern and South western Nigeria as Soyinka, Achebe, Okigbo, Amadi, Iyayi, Rotimi, Osofisan, and the female voices of Nwapa and Emecheta as representative Nigerian novelists. However, little or no scholarly attention has been given to the fictional works produced in northern Nigeria. It is against this background that this paper examines the oppression of women in northern Nigeria.

The scope of the study covers Zaynab Alkali's *The Descendants* and Abubakar Gimba's *Sacred Apples* with particular attention on their depiction of women oppression in Northern Nigeria. The paper also relies on secondary materials such as textbooks, journals and electronic materials.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopts feminism as its theoretical framework for analysing the primary texts. The term 'feminism' has been defined by various scholars and critics to reflect their diverse perspectives. *The Standard Encyclopedic College Dictionary* defines feminism “as a doctrine advocating the granting of the same social, political and economic right to women as the one granted to men, also a movement designed to support this doctrine and gain such rights” (223). It is a collective term for a system of beliefs and theories that pay special attention to women's rights and position in society. Similarly, feminism is a collection of movements aimed at defining, establishing and defending equal political, economic, and social rights for women (7). From the

above definitions, we can see that feminism seeks to address the social, cultural and economic inequalities and oppression faced by women in a patriarchal society. Feminism, as noted by Sarah Gamble, highlights the patriarchal nature of modern societies, where men hold more power and women face injustice. Archer further claims that feminism seeks to investigate how gender inequality works hand in glove with other social categories such as race, ethnicity and sexuality. Patricia notes that “feminism seeks a subjective identity, a sense of effective agency and history for women which has hitherto been denied them by dominant (male) culture” (9). The common factor of all feminist perspectives is gender consciousness. Feminist theory, as argued in this study, seeks to promote gender equality and justice between men and women. It argues that both men and women should be equally treated politically, economically and socially. Feminism revolves around proving that the difference between the sexes is nurtured and not natured. Therefore, feminism attempts to change the socially constructed and nurtured idea created in gender, as opposed to those made in nature. For this study, textual feminism that is based on the narration of women’s conditions and their textual representations shall be adopted.

However, feminist scholars have come up with different types of feminism, just as there are different analyses (by feminists) of the causes of gender inequalities. The most frequently cited are liberal, socialist (or Marxist), and radical perspectives. Nnolim (115) posits that "the contours of the feminist literary landscape in Africa in general and Nigeria in particular presents a panorama of ululating topography; it is a house divided in itself and at present, looks discomfortingly like the leaning Tower of Pisa." The foregoing assertion can simply be interpreted to mean that feminism cannot be described as a unified theoretical and philosophical discourse. It is rather characterised by various ideological differences, postulations and mutually irreconcilable cultural perceptions.

Because feminist discourse has a wide range of several sub-genres, this study adopts liberal feminism as a theoretical tool. Liberal feminism is concerned with gender equality in public sphere such as equal access to education, equal pay, and better working conditions for women and freedom from oppression and violence. Both Gimba's *Sacred Apples* and Zaynab's *The Descendants* align strongly with the liberal feminist discourse as they seek to promote better conditions of living for women through economic empowerment and access to education.

Review of Relevant Literature

Oppression of women in Northern Nigeria is occasioned majorly by early and forced marriage. Early and forced or arranged marriages are significant factors contributing to the oppression of women in Northern Nigeria. In Northern Nigeria, women have been subjected to oppression, depression, suppression, rejection and segregation and unfair and undue victimization. Zaynab Alkali, for instance, writes to deconstruct and at the same time to correct the evils of patriarchy in her society. The novelist captures this act of oppressing women in one of her novels, *Stillborn* through the characterisation of Li. Zaynab reveals this when Li's husband abandons her in the village for four years, marries to another wife in the city. Li suffers the stress of life and unfavourable treatment from her husband after she eventually reaches the city. Li however resolves to seek for freedom, independence that will bring happiness to her life. She successfully completes her studies which enables her to assume a position of leadership in her family.

In *Cobwebs and Other Stories*, Zaynab Alkali exposes the fate of the woman in society when she shows the suffering women go through to please their husbands while they go ahead to please others. Maya almost worships her husband and his family not knowing that he has a secret family somewhere else and enjoys life more than she does.

In *I'd Rather Die* by Audee T. Giwa, the novelist gives a panoramic insight of how women are treated and their psychological problems, the travails of a woman forced into marriage, the obstacle created for the woman in a patriarchal society, and the unpleasant marital experiences of women grossly caused by the misconception of Islamic religion. Mallam Umar, for instance, intends to forcefully marry Fatima to Alhaji Maikudi to have another source of money besides his salary, since his salary as a teacher is too small to maintain the family. Therefore, marrying Fatima to a rich man can be another source of income to the family. He forcefully gives his daughter out in marriage against her will as the only solution.

Again, Zaynab, Alhaji Maikudi's fourth wife is never given the opportunity to choose her own husband. It can be argued, from the above, that in Northern Nigeria, the woman is deprived of her basic rights to respect and dignity. In *I'd Rather Die*, the feelings and happiness of a woman are irrelevant. What matters is what the woman can bring through her marriage. Zaynab is virtually sold out by her parents because her father wants to have the latest vespa scooter and her mother a sewing machine, and the only way out to achieve these material things is to give their daughter to a man she does not love:

The money was there, her father who so much wanted to have a motorcycle, had the latest model of Vespa Scooter. Her mother who also loved a sewing machine had got a singer sewing machine. She wanted to be married to a young boy she loved but was given to a sixty-year-old man, old enough to be her grandfather (68).

Alabi et al further note that girl-children in their early years, about 12 or even less, are given out in marriage to friends, benefactors, strangers, visitors, elders, clerics etc. At times, even against

the wishes of these girls, they are married off to men old enough to be their grandfathers. Indeed, parents make a fortune through bride payments on their daughters. Even though the Child Rights Act (section 18) prohibits under-18 years old marriage in Nigeria, not all states in the North have domesticated the Act and many girls under 18 in the North are given out in marriage without their consent.

This is the reality of the girl child in Northern Nigeria and unfortunately, religious-cultural practices enhance this flagrant abuse of the rights of women and girls. Many scholars such as Ojaide, Kassam, Gordimer and Orabueze agree that culture and religion have deterred women to achieve their yearning and aspirations, in all spheres of life, in Northern Nigeria. However, Islam as religion has been misinterpreted or manipulated, especially by menfolk to justify the oppression of women in Northern Nigeria.

The predominantly Hausa and Fulani Muslim women in northern Nigeria are victims of cultural and religious dictates. Many of these practices are frequently rooted in the belief that women's roles are limited to domestic duties and childcare. This situation leads to unfair treatment of women, faced with early/arranged marriages, teenage pregnancy, physical and psychological violence, polygamy, divorce and are denied the chance to receive education. To support the above claim, Kabir (145) argues that "culture requests girls to marry early in life and this jeopardises their chances to pursue education." These girls allow traditional system to be used against them and to limit their possibilities within society.

Critical works abound that identify the problem of the woman in northern Nigeria, her plight and the things she goes through daily in works like Elsbeth Robson's *The 'Kitchen' as Women's Space in Rural Hausa land, Northern Nigeria*, and Novian Whitsitt's *Islamic-Hausa*

Feminism and Kano Market Literature: Qur'anic Reinterpretation in The Novels of Balaraba Yakubu.

Textual Analysis

The texts of Gimba and Alkali offer a nuanced portrayal of women, transitioning from victims of oppression to agents of change, who actively seek to overcome their subjection and forge their own paths. It is evident that the novelists utilise feminist theoretical lens in their works to reflect changing gender roles in society. This is a theme that is consistently echoed throughout their works. *The Descendants* and *Sacred Apples* are directly influenced and impacted by Islam, the dominant religion in the texts. The texts clarify thorny issues affecting the woman; it would appear the region suffers more feminist problems than other regions of Nigeria. These issues include the cultural and religious acceptance of polygamy, early marriage, girl-child education and purdah. Alkali and Gimba depict women's emancipation through education, particularly western education.

The female characters are employed by the novelists to bring about the emergence of the new northern Nigerian woman. They are portrayed as being in control of their situations and destinies. They maximise opportunities previously denied for self-fulfilment. Zaynab Alkali, for instance, portrays women as vibrant crusaders, who re-jig social developments. Seytu in *The Descendants* as the main voice of the woman is endowed with strength. She is hardworking and conscious of her world through education. Alkali, through the voice of Saytu, believes that the acquisition of formal education emancipates the woman and expands her horizon to take charge of her life:

She knew education is the master key to opportunities for a better life. Education opens doors and gives an individual options in life....They, unlike her sons, would have options, and only education can offer Them these options. That is why Magira Milli had seen to it that everybody went to school, including Saytu (13-15).

Alkali explores modern education as a tool of conscious raising and emancipation for women. No wonder Okereke says that “Education with its liberalising influence and its concomitant economic independence is of necessity a weapon of liberation for women from patriarchal subjugation” (114). Gimba also portrays education as a necessity and an eye-opener in his work. He presents all his female characters, except Salma, as educated women and in spite of all that happened to them, they were able to conquer. The story of Zahrah, for instance, is a testament to resilience; despite being divorced, she still moved forward with her life. Gimba describes Zahrah as “intelligent, assertive and having a career. A job that can guaranteed her an enviable independence, while remaining a wife” (54). Through the characterisation of Zahrah and Seytu, one sees the woman assuming a new role and doing so effectively. Alkali presents female characters that exhibit a high degree of self-awareness, a consciousness that comes with a search for identity, an identity that is independent of that of the man, marriage or family.

Alkali’s Seytu and Gimba’s Zahrah share many similarities, both characters experience divorce; suffer miscarriages in their second marriage and in both cases the marriages do not end well. A defining moment in their lives comes when they stand on equal footing with their male counterparts. For instance, Saytu is just a little girl when her uncle, Aji Ramta and his wife marry her off to the District Head of Dam, a man whose age is supposed to symbolise wisdom but who

acts contradictorily by abandoning her after almost destroying her future. Alkali laments, “Then with a pang of conscience he remembered how he has consented to Saytu’s marriage with the district head at the age of twelve, just six years after her father died” (28). The marriage resulted in Saytu’s vaginal being damaged during childbirth which led to her suffering from Vesico Vaginal Fistula (VVF). Again, the marriage between Mero and Usman is seen as a bitter pill that no one could swallow, not even Usman himself who marries a girl under his care, a supposed daughter. Usman marries Mero, a fourteen-year old girl whose father, Maina and mother died at Maiduguri Damboa Road by accident. He is meant to see her as a daughter since he does not have one but he turns her into an unfortunate wife. Alkali says:

Usman uncharacteristically shocked the village and rocked his little world by marrying the fourteen-year-old orphan girl Mero... What about her education? The once jovial and much loved little girl turned into ageing woman over night, sullen and indifferent to her future. It was as if she had died with her parents (80-81).

Even Usman himself confesses to have wronged her: “The little girl we brought up together, Maina and I, maybe I have made a bad mistake, Almighty God will pardon me, a mistake that will affect her life forever” (165).

Similarly, in Gimba’s *Sacred Apples*, the marriage between Zahrah and her husband, Yazid is marked by misfortune. Yazid appears to be a loving one until trouble erupts between her and her husband. A woman in spite of her husband’s decision to throw her out of his house still covers his shame in the presence of their children, especially when Umaymah, their eldest

daughter, asks why her father speaking harshly. Zahrah has this to say, “Angy? No...no...no... He is not angry... with me... or with anybody. He is not happy that is all...” (7).

Zahrah does all this just to cover up for her husband; what else could she have done as a wife than to cover up her husband’s nakedness? She loves him and tries to protect the sacredness of their marriage. She reasons out correctly, “Not just because of the children, she has intensely loved him before the children came, even before marriage” (50). Yet, Yazid divorced her not minding his religious teaching that says “she is not to be divorced for casual or trifling reasons”. The divorce is truly the beginning of her struggle as a single parent.

The issue of women oppression in Northern Nigeria is alarming and worth considering, particularly from the way the religion is being manipulated to comply with patriarchal dictates. In *Sacred Apples* by Abubakar Gimba, Zahrah laments: "Himm...religion... religion? When it comes to dealing with women or their wives, many men are guided more by their whims and passions than by principles or religion" (Gimba, 29). Here the novel bemoans the cultural influence rather than the religious interpretation. Gimba condemns the abuse of the process of polygamy rather than polygamy itself. He shows how men sometimes practise polygamy in a way that is injurious to their women. The passions of individuals obviously overshadow the teaching of the Islamic faith and, in the aftermath, place women at a disadvantaged position. Gimba portrays the ordeals of women in marriage even as he advocates education as an essential tool for challenging part of the inequalities.

In a patriarchal society reflected in *Sacred Apples*, the author does not condemn polygamy as an institution because of Islamic religious principles. However, through his main

character, he preaches against the docile, blind submissive, subjugated and dependent woman who sees her husband as an indispensable entity in the face of tyranny. Zahrah laments that:

Gimba believes that after several decades of feminist writings in the north, Muslim women have made a significant progress in their socio-economic standing. In line with this positive outlook, he creates a modern woman in the north who can be independent, confident, and intelligent, focused and face adversity with courage.

According to Kabir (11) "education and economic autonomy become avenue for survival for the oppressed women." In a related development, Urnar (9) argues that the thematic concerns of *Sacred Apples* suggests that Gimba subscribes to women's education at all levels. The concern for the girl child education constitutes what Gimba considers as the philosophy of national development. Armed with a university degree before her divorce with Yazid, Zahrah secures a job through the assistance of her brother, Shareef. With a paid job at hand, she braces up for the challenges of a nursing mother and a career woman in a public establishment. Through her job, she provides sustenance for her children while at the same time contributes to national productivity.

Udumukwu (68) writes that "Zaynab Alkali is alert to the fact that the actual dominant consciousness in her society stands in the way of woman's struggle to realise her freedom and define her identity", and says that "the reality of this actual dominant consciousness lies in its attempt to naturalise woman as inferior.... As a result, Alkali's work is focused on portraying the experiences and struggles of women, with a key role of raising awareness and consciousness about their condition, which she considers essential" (51). Some of the educated female

characters in Alkali's fiction consciously probe to find the elasticity limit to which their acquired education could accommodate their quest for freedom.

However, Seytu symbolises a radical shift in Alkali's liberal and accommodative feminism in a very fundamental way. While in some of her earlier works there is a discernible conviction that despite the glaring shortcomings occasioned by overt patriarchal dominance, there are still positive values and attributes to the institution of marriage which could be cherished and which Alkali defends. In *The Descendants* however, the educated women are so engrossed with their careers and could not care less about marriage. They would wish to get married, yes, but on their own terms. Dr. Glo Madina was willing, if possible to remain unmarried until her "Mr right" comes along, and Saytu as observed earlier "waltzes" out of her marriage to Yerima and piles "one marriage over another" (155) as she married Col Hassan without any indication that she divorced Yerima.

Similarly, *Sacred Apples* also interrogates several feminist issues including the notion that a woman must be under the control of man to have a fulfilled life. Guided by his socio-religious background, Gimba employs Zubaydah to prompt Zahrah to contemplate another marriage. Though Zahrah initially rejects the thought of re marrying, her grandmother becomes extremely bitter as Zahrah could visualise in her dream. The narrator points out:

She had no disdain for the institution itself, but the practice. Most men, she wanted to tell her grandmother, had bastardised the institution and turned marital homes into houses of horror for women. The limits and conditions set out in the Book for the practice have been conveniently ignored by many a man to the

greater detriment of women, resulting in abuses and humiliation that place some of them only a little bit above slaves. (Gimba, 194).

This oppressive attitude of men further supports the notion that in a patriarchal society depicted in the novel, the whims and passions overshadow the religious law. Zahrah later remarries despite the bitter experience attendant upon her first marriage. She marries Nousah, a man who shows love, compassion and understanding. However, the marriage which appears blissful and promising at the beginning starts to crumble because of the intrigues of Zahrah's co-wives. She finds herself in a polygamous family with all its attendant predicaments. The courage as well as the determination with which she withstands the intrigues and machinations of the co-wives is worth considering, Zahrah insists that:

It is a cultural outgrowth, and a malignant one, the institution of polygamy in our religion. The Holy Scripture exhorts men to treat women equally, yet, here we are fighting each other for preferential treatment, wanting superiority over each other, fighting for unequal treatment... It is not supposed to be so. We are all equal before our man and God. We only owe ourselves mutual respect. (Gimba, 175).

The above narrative shows that polygamy as a form of marriage is not inherently bad as portrayed by Zahrah and of course by many Northern Nigerian feminists. The problem lies squarely on envious individuals who are parties to it. This above opinion is in consonance with the submission of Abubakar Bilqisu (as cited in Yacim) that "People believe I hate polygamy but this is not so; it is the abuse of the institution that I dislike because I am a product of polygamy, and it is been a wonderful experience" (54).

Worugi, (29) believes that feminist organisations like the International Commission for Abolition of Sexual Mutilation (CAMS) founded in 1976, which proposed to work towards enhancing women's status in society through the abolition of institutionalised polygamy, obligatory motherhood and illiteracy of women failed to appreciate how polygamy is conceptualised in Islam. Zahrah does not show the readers that polygamy is bondage for the women. She shows an understanding of the gulf between what the religion preaches and what the traditional attitude of individual is, even though, it is obvious that she is caught between the desire to be a committed, dutiful wife and a working-class woman in an unfriendly polygamous home.

In the polygamous set up reflected by Gimba, Zahrah's second marriage turns out to be set for another trauma and failure. Remarkably, Zahrah depicts an embodiment of the modern educated woman, who, according to Asabe Yusuf still in Umar (533) is entangled in the web of two opposing forces: the assertiveness she receives from education and the passivity of cultural practices often encouraged by men to serve certain interests. Joseph, argues that:

The Qur'an provides the Muslim with a set of laws, values and principles that constitute a standard of conduct and a way of life. It proclaims the partnership of men and women and their equal spiritual and human values of each sex. However, local customs and male ascendancy in society have put women under men's control. (220).

The argument above implies that the Qur'an promotes a sense of equality and mutual respect between men and women, though traditional customs and male dominance have resulted in women being subordinate to men, limiting their autonomy and awareness in society. Gimba's

Sacred Apples brings Islam into the limelight by reflecting how religion is being misrepresented. The narrator, in a quite authorial voice, states clearly through Ya-Shareef, that "the problem has not been the blueprint (the religion, the Qu'ran). The problem has been the practice, adherence to commandments. The misapplication and outright violation, such is the nature of mankind" (304). In *Sacred Apples*, Gimba makes it clear that education, according to Islam, is not a prerogative of the men. The girl-child also needs to be supported by allowing her to acquire education so that she can take her pride of place in society. Gimba concludes his feminist religious outlook by denouncing the so-called superiority of men over women. He uses the last testament to mankind as the basis of his assertion that "women are equal to men. No more no less. Quite clearly the text, *Sacred Apples* states that "men are a degree above women, a degree of responsibility, not of superiority" (Gimba, 305).

The discussion above, regarding the representation of women's oppression in Gimba's *Sacred Apples* and Alkali's *The Descendants*, highlights the complexities of polygamy in Islam. While Islamic religion permits polygamy, by allowing a man to marry up to four wives (as stated in the Holy Qu'ran 4:3), it also emphasises the importance of treating all his wives with justice, fairness, and equal love. However, fulfilling these conditions becomes impossible as it is difficult for a man to provide equal treatment and love to his wives. In the texts, polygamy is presented as destructive to family harmony and an aid to women's oppression. For instance, Saytu's friend tells her this when she finds out that Saytu is getting married to Yerima Gamma: "up to date he had several divorces and numerous children" (135). Yerima has the financial strength to pick any woman at will not minding the Qur'an's condition for such. According to Lemu, "of all the things Allah has made lawfull, divorce is the most hateful to him" (7). He had seven children from previous marriages and a very senior wife yet, he is billed to marry a sixteen-year-old

daughter of the Emir of Kudu: at the same time, he is getting married to Saytu. What other form of oppression or subjugation can be meted out to women than to be packed like sardines under one man.

As argued in Attachment Theory, John and Mary believe that emotional bonds can form differently with each person, influenced by shared experiences, personality, and individual connections. They also note that love is a complex mix of emotion which can be expressed differently in each relationship. Therefore, given the fact that a man cannot equally treat all his wives has informed some scholars such as Arlie Hochschild to argue that polygamy, despite being permitted in Islam, can perpetuate women's subjugation and reinforce gender disparities in northern societies.

Conclusion

Zaynab Alkali and Abubakar Gimba are dominant literary voices from Northern Nigeria. These writers reflect the challenges that women face. Alkali and Gimba present strong, assertive, and educated female characters, who make choices that affect their lives. They portray women that overcome entrenched religious, cultural and economic obstacles and subsequently make significant contributions to the development of society. The two texts studied emphasise and highlight the ability women possess to face challenges thrown at them. The authors show how in overcoming such challenges, the woman makes society a better place.

These fictions chronicle the tremendous and steady metamorphosis of the woman in society, a corresponding reality of what she is in the contemporary northern community. The contribution of the woman in society is identified and brought to the fore. She brings change. Her natural capacities like: the maternal instincts, the nurturing traits that make her selfless, her

capacity for resilience in the face of opposition, her keen perception of needs, strength of will, resolution, love, compassion and kindness. All these make her a force that keeps society on the right track, especially where it is coupled with education. It is shown to be the essential means with which the girl-child is empowered with skills, knowledge and self-confidence necessary to actively and fully drive development.

The fictive narratives show the woman determining her destiny. She is breaking the negative control of religion, culture and tradition that are tailor-made to subjugate her. The authors tacitly call for a new paradigm shift, a synergy between men and women, where a better world, with equity, fairness and justice is created. The novels uncover the fallacy of religious and cultural practices which kept women perpetually down for a long time. The writers call for a harmonious co-existence between the sexes through the provision of education, which creates a level playing ground for genders.

The novels reflect the importance of education for the girl-child in northern Nigeria. They bring awareness that women can contribute meaningfully to the needed development in the nation if empowered with education. They equipped the female characters with sound education to speak out loud, to be heard on economic and socio-political issues. This study finds that the education of the girlchild in northern Nigeria has not been fully mainstreamed, but appreciable progress is ongoing. The girl needs educational encouragement to enable her succeed in all facets of life. The study observes that education is the most important tool in the empowerment of the girl-child in Nigeria, especially in the Northern region.

Alkali and Gimba have created a new image of female characters unlike older depictions, who are no longer dependent or weak. They create images of educationally empowered,

independent, and strong women. These female characters show total disregard for the patriarchal and religious systems and attain positive achievements. The study also presented a viable means to reverse the ugly trend of the North perpetually being regarded as educationally empowered, independent and strong women. These female characters show total disregard for the patriarchal and religious systems and attain positive achievements. It shows that educating the woman is educating the nation, as women strive to educate themselves, they thereafter ensure that those under their influence also acquire education and contribute to society.

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